

TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES AND CORROSION RESISTANCE OF NANODIAMOND REINFORCED COMPOSITE COATINGS ON NITI ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Ni-P/nanodiamond (ND) nanocomposite coatings with various ND contents were prepared by electrodeposition in Ni-P electrolyte containing different concentration of ND particles. The effects of ND particles on the composition, structure, distribution of ND and microhardness of nanocomposite coatings were investigated. The results showed that co-deposited ND was uniformly distributed in the Ni-P matrix, and led to the changes in the composition and structure of Ni-P/ND composite coatings, contributing to the increase of the microhardness of Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings compared with the Ni-P coating. The corrosion behavior of Ni-P and Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings was evaluated by polarization curves and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy in artificial saliva at 37°C. It was found that the introduction of ND in Ni-P matrix increased the corrosion resistance. Ni-P and Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings prepared from electrolyte containing 0.5-8.0 g/L ND exhibited active-passive transition, while Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings obtained from electrolyte with ND concentration of 15.0 g/L behaved active dissolution. In general, Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings obtained from Ni-P electrolyte containing 8.0g/L ND exhibited excellent wear and corrosion properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite electroplating allows the co-deposit of the inert particles such as oxides, carbides, nitrides, metal powder and so on, with the plated metals or alloys in order to improve the surface properties. With the development of nanotechnology and nanomaterials, nano-sized particles gradually substitute micro-sized particles to incorporate in the composite coatings for reinforcement, leading to the further improvement of the properties of composite coatings.

Up till now, various nano particulates have been used in nanocomposite coatings, such as nano-SiC^[1], nano-Al₂O₃^[2], nano-TiO₂^[3], nano-ZrO₂^[4], nano-Si₃N₄^[5], carbon nanotubes (CNT)^[6] and nanodiamond (ND)^[7-9]. Among them, ND has attracted increasingly scientific interest by virtue of their unique mechanical and tribological properties such as high hardness, low friction coefficient and good chemical stability, as well as the characteristics of nano-sized particles.

Ni-P coatings have been extensively used in industry due to their excellent properties including high hardness, good corrosion resistance, superior wear resistance and environmental friendliness. Generally, there are two methods to prepare Ni-P coatings, including electroless plating and electrodeposition. The electroplating has some advantages over electroless plating, such as operating at low temperature, stability of the electrolyte and less brittleness of the coatings. However, few has been reported on the incorporation of ND particles in the electrodeposited Ni-P coatings, though it has been known that ND particles as a filler contribute to improve the antiwear ability and corrosion resistance of electroless Ni-P composites. In the present study, different amounts of ND were incorporated into Ni-P matrix by electroplating method and the effects of ND on the structure,

composition, microhardness and the corrosion resistance in artificial saliva of Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings was investigated.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ni-Ti alloy (Ti-50.8at.%Ni) plate with the size of 12mm×9mm×1mm was used as cathode, and was sequentially grinded with SiC paper, polished, insulated of unplated parts, measured the areas of electroplated parts, cleaned with alkali solution at 353K, electrolytic activated in HF-HNO₃ solution till red smoke produced, and then in HCl-H₂SO₄ solution for 5 minutes. Between every step the samples were rinsed with distilled water.

Nanodiamond (ND) used in this study was purchased from HE YUAN ZHONG LIAN Nanotechnology Co., LTD. (China). Prior to use, ND particles were firstly mechanically balling in PEG solution for 2h, and then purified in HNO₃-H₂SO₄ mixed solutions at 363K for 5h, followed by washing with distilled water till pH=7 and dried by freezing-drying method. Different amounts (0.5g/L, 2g/L, 8g/L, 15g/L) of ND particles with the average size of 4-15nm was added into the Ni-P electrolyte containing NiSO₄·6H₂O 220g/l, NiCl₂·6H₂O 45g/L, NaH₂PO₂ 60g/L, H₃BO₃ 30g/L and NaF 20g/L with the pH of 2.2 ~ 2.4.

Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings were prepared from Ni-P plating bath containing various ND concentration on NiTi substrate at the current density of 2 A/dm² at 343K. The average thickness of the coating were approximately 20-35 μm for a deposition time of 2h. During the process of electrodeposition, the electrolyte was magnetic stirring at a moderate rate of 450rpm. For controls, pure Ni-P coatings were prepared under the same condition.

The content and distribution of ND in Ni-P/ND composite coatings were studied by using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, MX2600FE, Britain) equipped with an attachment for energy dispersive X-ray analyzer system (EDX) in the back-scattering electron (BSE) mode. The ND content of the composite coatings were determined by the carbon content of the composite coatings. Three measurements were made and averaged in all cases. The structure of Ni-P coating and Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings were identified by X-ray diffractometer (XRD, X'Pert ProMPD, Netherlands).

The microhardness and wear resistance of the composite coatings were studied on the mechanically polished surface of the coatings. The microhardness of the coatings was tested on HVS-1000 microhardness tester using a load of 100g and a dwelling time of 5s. Five readings were taken and then the values were averaged. The sliding wear and friction tests of the coatings was performed on a wear machine in ball-on-disc mode with a load of 4N, a rotating speed of 300rpm and the overall rotation of 8000r under ambient conditions without lubrication. The silicon nitride ball (~HV1500) was used as the counter body. The coefficients of the friction were obtained by measuring the tangential force on the specimen using a strain gauge bridge and recorded by a software on computer. The weight loss of the samples was measured by using an electronic balance with 0.1mg weight scale accuracy, and the wear rate (mg/mm) was calculated by dividing the weight loss by the total sliding wear distance. The morphologies of the worn out surfaces were observed by SEM.

A conventional three-electrode cell was used for the electrochemical investigations, using a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and a platinum electrode as counter electrode. The working electrode was Ni-P and Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coating with an expressed area of 0.2826 cm². The corrosion test was carried out on a CHI600A Potentiostat/galvanostat system in artificial saliva containing NaCl 0.4 g/L, KCl 0.4 g/L, CaCl₂ 0.78g/L, NaH₂PO₄·H₂O 0.69g/L, Na₂S·9H₂O 0.005g/L, KSCN 0.3g/L and Urea 1.0g/L with pH 5.6 at 310K. Potentiodynamic polarization curves were performed at a scanning rate of 0.33mV/s and the scanning range was from -700 mV to 2000 mV. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was carried out at open circuit potential with applied frequencies ranging from 10⁵ to 10⁻² Hz with the amplitude of 10 mV.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is well known that a sufficient dispersion of nanoparticles in the composite coating plays a significant role in the strengthening effect of composite coating. However, it is difficult to achieve good dispersion of nanoparticles in aqueous solution which tend to agglomerate due to its large surface

areas and high surface energy. In order to reduce the tendency of agglomeration of nanodiamond (ND) particles in composite coatings, ND particles were treated by the combination of mechanical balling and acid functionalization in H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 mixed solutions. Fig.1 shows the XRD patterns and FT-IR spectra of as-received and dispersion-treated ND particles. As can be seen, broadened diffraction peaks appeared at 44° , 75° and 92° according to (111), (220) and (311) of cubic diamond structure, respectively, indicating that the dispersion treatment procedure did not change the structure of ND.

Furthermore, the FT-IR spectra shown in Fig. 1(b) indicated that the characteristic absorption peak of diolefine at about 3000cm^{-1} was weakened, while the peaks at 1735cm^{-1} and 1392cm^{-1} attributing to carboxy group appeared after dispersion treatment. The change of functional group on the surface of ND indicated the improvement of hydrophilicity of ND, which is beneficial for the homogeneous dispersion of ND in the plating solution.

Fig. 1 (a) XRD patterns and (b) FT-IR spectra of nanodiamond in as-received and dispersion-treated state

Surface morphology of the as-deposited Ni-P alloy coating and Ni-P/ND composite coatings is shown in Fig. 2. It is indicated that the incorporation of ND particles in the electroplated Ni-P matrix increased the surface roughness of the resultant coating.

Fig. 2 SEM surface morphology of (a) Ni-P alloy coating, (b) Ni-P/ND composite coating (containing %ND) (c) and (d) magnified image of (b)

According to the published reports^[10-13], composite coatings are considered to be rougher than the particle-free coatings due to the entrapment of particles. In addition, the electroplated Ni-P/ND composite coating consisted of a homogeneous globular structure, in which the ND particles tended to form the agglomerates in the submicron range and were embedded in the Ni-P matrix through a co-deposition process, as seen in magnified images (Fig. 2 (b) and (c)) of Ni-P/ND composite coatings. The EDX patterns taken on Ni-P alloy coating and Ni-P/ND composite coating indicated that the chemical composition of coating changed from 17.1 wt.% P and 73.6wt.% Ni, 1.8wt.% O, 7.5wt.% C to 15.6wt.% P, 47.8wt.% Ni, 19.4 wt.% O and 17.3wt.% C with the incorporation of ND particles in the electroplated Ni-P matrix. The sharp increase of carbon content was attributed to the incorporation of ND particles in the Ni-P matrix.

Fig.3 shows the BSE micrographs of polished Ni-P-ND nanocomposite coatings. It was observed that ND particles dispersed uniformly in Ni-P matrix, and with the ND concentration increasing from 0.5g/L to 8g/L, the ND amount incorporated in Ni-P matrix increased as well. However, when the ND concentration was up to 15g/L, ND particles tended to agglomerate in the local region and some clusters in micrometer scale formed.

Fig. 3. BSE images of polished Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings at various ND concentrations in Ni-P electrolyte (a) 0.5 g/L, (b) 2.0 g/L, (c) 8.0 g/L and (d) 15.0 g/L

The composition of Ni-P/ND composite coatings was presented in Fig. 4(a). The ND content increased slightly with increasing the ND concentration in the plating bath from 0.5 g/L to 8.0 g/L, and then decreased greatly at 15 g/L. Fig. 4(b) shows the XRD patterns of Ni-P and Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings at various ND concentrations in plating bath. The diffraction peak of Ni-P alloy coating was lower and broader, indicating the amorphous structure of Ni-P coatings. When ND particles were introduced into Ni-P matrix, the diffraction peaks became higher and sharper with the increasing amount of ND in Ni-P matrix. The size of crystallite for Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings was evaluated by Scherer formula, and the results are illustrated in Table 1. It is showed that the size of crystallite decrease with the ND concentration changing from 0.5 g/L to 8.0g/L, and then increased greatly when ND concentration was 15 g/L, indicating that the addition of ND in Ni-P matrix changed the structure of Ni-P coatings from amorphous to nano-crystalline, and the grain refinement effect of ND particles firstly increased with the increase of ND concentration in plating bath, and then decreased due to the agglomeration of ND in Ni-P coatings at the concentration of 15 g/L. This may due to the addition of ND particles, which provided more nucleus for Ni-P alloy during the co-deposition process, resulting in the increase of the nucleation ability of the nanocomposite coatings increased with increasing ND concentration in the plating bath. On the other hand, further increase of

ND concentration in the electrolyte increased the probability of collision and aggregation between ND particles. The formed agglomerates not only decreased the grain refinement effect, but exerted an effect on the co-deposition process, leading to the decrease of the properties of nanocomposite coatings.

Fig.4. (a) Chemical composition and (b) X-ray diffraction patterns of Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings prepared from various concentration of the ND particles in the plating bath.

Table 1 Grain size of Ni-P/nanodiamond composite coatings

Nanodiamond content (g/l)	2 Theta (deg.)	FWHM (rad)	Grain size (nm)
0.5	44.52	0.064	2.2
2	44.57	0.067	2.1
8	44.64	0.09	1.6
16	44.51	0.03	4.8

The hardness and wear rate of as-deposited and heat-treated Ni-P/ND composite coatings are illustrated in Fig.5 and Fig.6. Compared with the hardness of Ni-P alloy coatings (600MPa), the hardness of Ni-P/ND composite coatings was higher due to the strengthening effect of dispersion hardening of the incorporated ND particles. The hardness of Ni-P/ND composite coating firstly increased with increasing ND concentration from 0.5g/L to 8.0g/L, and then decreased at the concentration of 15 g/L, which was probably owing to the agglomeration of ND in Ni-P matrix with higher ND content in the electroplating. In addition, compared with the hardness of coatings in as-deposited condition, the hardness increased greatly due to the precipitation of nickel phosphide (Ni₃P), which is confirmed by XRD measurement (Fig.4). This observation was in agreement with the results reported by other researchers^[14].

The relationship between the wear rate and ND content of Ni/ND composited coatings was similar to that of hardness, which could be seen in Fig. 6. The Ni/ND composited coatings prepared from the electroplating containing 8 g/L ND exhibited better wear property than other case.

Fig.7 shows the corrosion behavior of Ni-P and Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings in artificial saliva solution. It can be seen from polarization curves (Fig.7 (a)) that only Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings prepared from 15g/L ND concentration electrolyte exhibited active dissolution behavior, all other coatings showed active-passive transition behavior. In addition, the introduction of ND in Ni-P matrix caused the shift towards positive of the corrosion potential compared with Ni-P coatings, indicating lower corrosion tendency of Ni-P/ND composite coatings compared with Ni-P coatings.

Fig. 5. The relation curve of the microhardness of Ni-P/nanodiamond composite and the nanodiamond content in the plating bath

Fig. 6. The wear rate of Ni-P/nanodiamond composite coatings

Fig.7. (a) Polarization potentiodynamic curves (b) Nyquist diagrams of impedance spectrum of Ni-P and Ni-P/ND coatings measured in artificial saliva solution at pH=5.6.

A convenient way to evaluate the corrosion properties of the samples is to compare the diameters of the semi-circles in Nyquist plot^[15]. The larger the diameter is, the better corrosion resistance of the sample was expected^[16]. As can be seen from Fig.4 (b), the Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings exhibited larger diameters than Ni-P coatings, indicating better corrosion resistance after the

introduction of ND in Ni-P matrix. For the ND particles, on the one hand, they may act as inert physical barriers to the initiation and development of defect corrosion, hence improved the corrosion resistance of the coating^[17,18], such as Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings prepared from plating bath with 0.5-8.0g/L ND concentration. On the other hand, ND particles decrease the active surface area of the cathode owing to the adsorption of ND and might also relate to the decrease in the ionic transportation by ND, which did not significantly affect the electrochemical reaction mechanism. This observation conforms to what was reported by other researchers^[6,19].

4 CONCLUSIONS

Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings with different ND content were successfully deposited on Ni-Ti shape memory alloy substrates. ND particles distributed uniformly in Ni-P matrix, and changed the structure of Ni-P matrix from amorphous to nano-crystalline. Due to the dispersion strengthening effect of ND particles, Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings prepared from ND concentration in the electrolyte ranging from 0.5g/L to 8.0g/L, the microhardness of Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings was higher than that of Ni-P coating, and possessed higher corrosion resistance. In the case of Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings obtained from Ni-P electrolyte containing 15.0g/L, ND aggregated in Ni-P matrix, resulting in decreased microhardness and corrosion resistance, while Ni-P/ND nanocomposite coatings obtained from Ni-P electrolyte containing 8.0g/L ND exhibited excellent wear and corrosion properties.

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